

USING COMPUTERS IN TEACHING THE PAST CONTINUOUS TENSE AS ONE OF THE EFFECTIVE WAYS OF FORMING GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE FOR A1 LEVEL PUPILS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8037785>

Abstarct: Technology is one of the best methods in current lessons as all children are keen on computers or other types of electrical appliances. The aim of the article is to discuss some methods of lessons which are used computers to teach young souls. The article illustrates the usage of computers in teaching past tense for school children for A1 degrees.

Key words: computer, technology, method, past tense,

Learning the basic structure and usage of the past continuous is usually not that difficult for most students. Unfortunately, this is not the case when it comes to actively integrating the past continuous into everyday conversations or written communications. This lesson is aimed at helping students actively use the past continuous in speaking and writing. This is done through the use of the past continuous as a descriptive tense to "paint a picture" in words of the moment when something important occurred.

Begin teaching the past continuous by telling a story with exaggerated details through the use of the past continuous. For example: "I remember that day well. The birds were singing, the sun was shining, and the children were playing games peacefully. At that moment, I saw Alex and fell in love." Point out how the past continuous is used to paint a picture of the scene. Quickly review the past continuous structure with the class. Go over differences in usage between the past simple and past continuous. Point out that the past continuous focuses on a specific moment in the past. Write various examples on the board of sentences combining the past simple and past continuous to illustrate the idea of an interrupted past. For example, "I was walking through the park when I met David." Ask students to comment on what function the past continuous plays in the example sentences. Have students divide into small groups of 3-4. Ask students to complete the activity by providing an appropriate response with the past continuous to describe an action that was interrupted. Next, have students first conjugate verbs in the past simple to complete the story. Next, ask them to insert past continuous clauses into the appropriate place in the story.

As a primary school teacher, you'll develop schemes of work and lesson plans in line with curriculum objectives. You'll facilitate learning by establishing a relationship with pupils, keeping your learning resources organized and creating a positive learning environment in the classroom.

Your role is to develop and foster the appropriate skills and social abilities to enable the optimum development of children, according to age, ability and aptitude.

You'll assess and record progress and prepare pupils for national tests. You'll link pupils' knowledge to earlier learning and develop ways to encourage it further, challenging and inspiring pupils to help them deepen their knowledge and understanding.

Primary schools (differing from Uzbek schools) in England (following the national curriculum) are usually divided into:

Foundation Stage - nursery and reception (ages three to five)Key Stage 1 - years one and two (ages five to seven)Key Stage 2 - years three to six (ages 7 to 11).

Primary schools in Wales (following the national curriculum and Foundation Phase) are typically divided into:

Foundation Phase (ages three to seven)Key Stage 2 (ages 7 to 11).A new curriculum and assessment framework is being rolled out in schools across Wales. This means that education in Wales will become one seamless curriculum for pupils aged 3 to 16 years old.

The benefits of using computers in the classroom goes beyond more efficient assessment and opportunities for online learning. Mobile devices and technologies are an inevitable part of society, but that does not mean that students naturally understand how to use those technologies appropriately. Using computers in the classroom gives teachers an opportunity to teach digital citizenship skills that demonstrate ways to use technology correctly and responsibly.

Computers also help maximize student engagement. Modern students are regularly exposed to technology outside of the classroom. Most use and enjoy smart phones and other mobile devices, which is why they are more likely to engage in the learning process if it involves something to which they are already accustomed and enjoy.

Computers have revolutionized the teaching profession in multiple ways. Teachers use computers to record grades, calculate averages, manage attendance and access data on student performance in online programs and assessments. Computers have also made it easier for teachers to vary their instructional delivery. Instead of lecturing at the front of the room for an entire class period, teachers can incorporate technology into their lessons to keep students engaged while appealing to a variety of learning styles. From using computers to create presentations on a topic to showing video clips that complement the lesson at hand, technology helps teachers make the content easier for students to understand.

As technology continues to lead society's future, computers in the classroom are a common sight. From elementary grades throughout graduate school, schools are granting approval for the use of computers in the classroom. Each school is different regarding the use and frequency of computers in school and there are debates regarding the benefits and the risks. Whether schools allow students to have individual computers or allow time in computer labs, one thing is certain: more children are using computers in their off-school hours and are becoming proficient in modern technology. For those who have used computers in the classroom, the benefits are unquestionable. More teachers are finding the connection with computers one that enhances and benefits students' learning and expands knowledge; however, teachers must supervise all computer use in order to achieve the greatest educational benefits. Children and teens should never have free access to surf websites unsupervised in the classroom. Modes of Instruction and Learning Using individual computers in the classroom often falls under the category of blended learning. This style of learning is when instructors incorporate several methods for delivering content to students. Some teachers use computers with special needs students as tools to help overcome communication issues. Computers may be used to help share assignments, engage in various activities, provide real-time communication experiences with others regardless the distance, enhance or expand lessons and increase knowledge. Mobile computing is becoming a popular

mode of learning and schools are embracing technology outside of the computer lab and in the classroom.

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